

PITUITARY ADENOMA TREATMENT APPROACHES AND TACTICS OF PATIENT MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: A pituitary adenoma is a tumor of the endocrine system, the manifestations of which are hyper- or hyposecretion of hormones of the anterior pituitary gland, as well as clinical symptoms caused by the impact of the neoplasm on the anatomical structures surrounding the sellar region. Among intracranial tumors, pituitary adenomas occupy third place, accounting for 7.3 to 18% of all verified brain tumors and affecting mainly people of working age, which accounts for about 75% of all cases of the disease. Pituitary adenomas are quite common (15-17%). Chronic hyperproduction of adenohypophysis hormones reduces the quality of life.

Keywords: giant pituitary adenomas; diagnostics; treatment

With hyperprolactinemia, about 30% of patients are infertile. Mortality in corticotropic and somatotropic pituitary tumors exceeds the population mortality rate by 5-10 times. At autopsy, pituitary adenomas are found in 25% of deceased people without any indication of endocrine diseases. The incidence of tumors increases with age. Hyperplasia of pituitary cells usually occurs under the influence of the hypothalamus. Tumors develop most often when one cell mutates and gets out of physiological control usually they are monoclonal, but there may be a tumor from one clone, and then a relapse, but from another clone. The pituitary gland contains the most somatotrophs (40-50%), therefore the largest tumors are somatotropinomas, then prolactotrophs (15-25%), corticotrophs (10-20%), gonadotrophs (10%) and thyrotrophs (5%).

Pituitary adenomas are tumors of monoclonal origin. They are heterogeneous in their morphological structure and have receptors for hypothalamic factors, and are also capable of synthesizing and secreting adenohypophysis hormones, neurohormones, and growth factors. Adenomas have different growth rates and different invasiveness. Pituitary tumors in 95.7% of cases are benign and slow-growing, however, the development of neuro-ophthalmological and endocrinological disorders in patients, and in some cases - focal neurological symptoms, causes the need to make a decision on the possibility of surgical, radiation or other methods of treatment. A distinction is made between microprolactinomas (size up to 10 mm), macroprolactinomas (more than 10 mm) or giant prolactinomas (more than 4 cm).

Clinical manifestations of pituitary adenomas (mass effect) are:

- compression of normal pituitary tissue and development of adenohypophysis cell atrophy
- hyperprolactinemia due to compression of the pituitary stalk
- headaches
- compression of the optic-chiasmatic crossing
- compression of the III, IV, VI pairs of cranial nerves, 1st and 2nd branches of the trigeminus (with tumor expansion into the cavernous sinus)

- intracranial hypertension with development of hydrocephalus (with compression of the floor of the III ventricle).

Most often, pituitary tumors occur at the age of 30-60 years.

As the tumor grows, there is a consistent loss of pituitary tropic function with a decrease in the levels of luteinizing hormone, follicle-stimulating hormone, thyroid-stimulating hormone, and adrenocorticotrophic hormone against the background of functional hyperprolactinemia. The endocrine manifestation of pituitary adenoma can be partial or complete (in macroadenomas) hypopituitarism, which often results in reproductive health disorders. The most common initial symptoms were decreased potency (in 57.9% of patients), visual field defects (in 11.6% of patients), headache (in 11.3%). According to other authors, reproductive disorders can occur in 78.3% of patients with inactive pituitary adenomas.

Diagnosis of pituitary adenomas

If a pituitary adenoma is suspected, it is necessary to conduct a craniography (sella turcica), an examination by an endocrinologist, an ophthalmologist (visual fields), and visualize the pituitary gland using MRI/CT. MRI is preferable to CT. But in some cases, both MRI and CT are indicated. In emergency cases or in patients with contraindications for MRI, CT is an acceptable alternative. Studies should be conducted in centers with sufficient experience in conducting such studies. It is necessary to clarify the nature of hormonal studies and refer the patient to a specialized clinic.

A feature of hormonal studies is that a single determination of the hormone content in the blood serum most often does not provide reliable information. Blood sampling should be done taking into account physiological influences. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) allows to examine the structure of the pituitary gland, identify and assess the size and prevalence of space-occupying pituitary lesions (adenomas, cysts, craniopharyngiomas, etc.), determine the presence of hemorrhages and their duration, and assess the effectiveness of conservative and surgical treatment. MRI allows to identify a tumor, as well as to assess its position in the sella turcica and its relationship with the surrounding brain structures, primarily with the chiasm and optic nerves.

Despite the leading role of instrumental examination methods in the diagnosis of pituitary adenomas, anamnestic and clinical data help to diagnose the presence of an adenoma at earlier stages of the disease.

Treatment of giant pituitary adenomas. Comprehensive examination of patients (determination of blood serum hormones, use of tests to determine a particular type of hormonal deficiency; computed tomography and/or MRI; development of optical technology and microsurgery) can significantly improve the results of surgical treatment. The possibility of more radical tumor removal has expanded while reducing postoperative mortality. However, despite the successes achieved, the problem of treating patients with pituitary adenomas is far from being solved [14–18]. Nevertheless, to date, there is no algorithm for correcting hormonal disorders in patients with pituitary adenomas in the early and late postoperative periods, which largely determines the quality of life. Giant pituitary adenomas with a maximum diameter of at least 40 mm continue to pose high surgical risks, despite advances in microsurgical and/or endoscopic surgery. Thus, Japanese authors concluded that preoperative embolization of giant pituitary adenoma is a useful procedure that can potentially reduce morbidity and mortality from this devastating tumor.

N. Nishioka et al. [16] presented a series of giant hormonally inactive adenomas and pointed out the limitations of effective and safe resection of giant pituitary tumors. In total, 93 patients (72.7%) underwent complete or subtotal tumor resection. The authors concluded that, regardless of the surgical approach, large intracranial traction, irregular configuration, and invasion are factors limiting effective resection.

According to T. Graillon et al. [8], the transcranial approach to tumor removal remains in demand for giant and invasive pituitary adenomas in conditions of inaccessibility of the transsphenoidal approach. In this case, the possibility of vascular complications, visual impairment, preoperative symptoms of patients, and benign features of the tumor should be taken into account

Conclusions

In the diagnostic complex for giant pituitary adenomas, in addition to clinical examination, it is necessary to use a full range of neuroimaging methods to determine the location of the chiasm, the extent of tumor spread to the base of the skull and the destruction of the latter. Surgical treatment is the method of choice when diagnosing giant pituitary adenoma, with the exception of isolated cases of STH- and prolactin-secreting tumors, in which treatment with dopamine agonists is possible. At the same time, for giant pituitary adenomas (diameter more than 4 cm), there is no single algorithm for the optimal surgical strategy.

References:

1. ERGASHEVA, G. T. (2024). OBESITY AND OVARIAN INSUFFICIENCY. *Valeology: International Journal of Medical Anthropology and Bioethics*, 2(09), 106-111.
2. Ergasheva, G. T. (2024). Modern Methods in the Diagnosis of Autoimmune Thyroiditis. *American Journal of Bioscience and Clinical Integrity*, 1(10), 43-50.
3. Tokhirovna, E. G. (2024). COEXISTENCE OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES. *TADQIQOTLAR. UZ*, 40(3), 55-62.
4. Toxirovna, E. G. (2024). DETERMINATION AND STUDY OF GLYCEMIA IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS WITH COMORBID DISEASES. *TADQIQOTLAR. UZ*, 40(3), 71-77.
5. Toxirovna, E. G. (2024). XOMILADORLIKDA QANDLI DIABET KELTIRIB CHIQARUVCHI XAVF OMILLARINI ERTA ANIQLASH USULLARI. *TADQIQOTLAR. UZ*, 40(3), 63-70.
6. Toxirovna, E. G. (2024). QANDLI DIABET 2-TIP VA KOMORBID KASALLIKLARI BO'LGAN BEMORLARDA GLIKEMIK NAZORAT. *TADQIQOTLAR. UZ*, 40(3), 48-54.
7. Tokhirovna, E. G. (2024). MECHANISM OF ACTION OF METFORMIN (BIGUANIDE) IN TYPE 2 DIABETES. *JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH*, 3(5), 210-216.
8. Tokhirovna, E. G. (2024). THE ROLE OF METFORMIN (GLIFORMIN) IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(4), 171-177.
9. Эргашева, Г. Т. (2024). Эффект Применения Бигуанида При Сахарным Диабетом 2 Типа И Covid-19. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 3(3), 55-61.
10. Toxirovna, E. G. (2024). QANDLI DIABET 2 TUR VA YURAK QON TOMIR KASALLIKLARINING BEMOLARDA BIRGALIKDA KECHISHI. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(7), 202-209.

- 11.Эргашева, Г. Т. (2024). СОСУЩЕСТВОВАНИЕ ДИАБЕТА 2 ТИПА И СЕРДЕЧНО-СОСУДИСТЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 38(7), 219-226.
- 12.Эргашева, Г. Т. (2024). СНИЖЕНИЕ РИСКА ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ У БОЛЬНЫХ САХАРНЫМ ДИАБЕТОМ 2 ТИПА И СЕРДЕЧНО-СОСУДИСТЫМИ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯМИ. Образование Наука И Инновационные Идеи В Мире, 38(7), 210-218.
- 13.Tokhirovna, E. G. (2024). CLINICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE COURSE OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION. Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования, 12(4), 234-243.
- 14.Tokhirovna, E. G. Studying the Causes of the Relationship between Type 2 Diabetes and Obesity. Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN, 2456-6470.
- 15.Toxirovna, E. G. (2024). ARTERIAL GIPERTENZIYA KURSINING KLINIK VA MORFOLOGIK JIHATLARI. Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования, 12(4), 244-253.
- 16.Эргашева, Г. Т. (2024). НОВЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ТЕЧЕНИЕ АРТЕРИАЛЬНОЙ ГИПЕРТОНИИ У ВЗРОСЛОГО НАСЕЛЕНИЕ. Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования, 12(4), 224-233.
- 17.Эргашева, Г. Т. (2024). ФАКТОРЫ РИСКА РАЗВИТИЯ САХАРНОГО ДИАБЕТА 2 ТИПА. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 36(5), 70-74.
- 18.Эргашева, Г. Т. (2024). ОСЛОЖНЕНИЯ САХАРНОГО ДИАБЕТА 2 ТИПА ХАРАКТЕРНЫ ДЛЯ КОГНИТИВНЫХ НАРУШЕНИЙ. TADQIQOTLAR. UZ, 30(3), 112-119.
- 19.Эргашева, Г. Т. (2023). Исследование Причин Связи Диабета 2 Типа И Ожирения. Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies, 2(12), 305-311.
- 20.Tokhirovna, E. G. (2024). Risk factors for developing type 2 diabetes mellitus. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 36(5), 64-69.
- 21.Toxirovna, E. G. (2024). QANDLI DIABET 2-TUR VA O'LIMNI KELTIRIB CHIQRUVCHI SABABLAR. Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования, 14(4), 86-93.
- 22.Tokhirovna, E. G. (2023). Study of clinical characteristics of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in middle and old age. Journal of Science in Medicine and Life, 1(4), 16-19.
- 23.Toxirovna, E. G. (2024). GIPERPROLAKTINEMIYA KLINIK BELGILARI VA BEPUSHTLIKKA SABAB BO'LUVCHI OMILLAR. Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования, 14(4), 168-175.
- 24.Toxirovna, E. G. (2023). QANDLI DIABET 2-TUR VA SEMIZLIKNING O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIK SABABLARINI O'RGANISH. Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi, 10(3), 168-173.
- 25.Saidova, L. B., & Ergashev, G. T. (2022). Improvement of rehabilitation and rehabilitation criteria for patients with type 2 diabetes.
- 26.Эргашева, Г. Т. (2023). Изучение Клинических Особенности Больных Сахарным Диабетом 2 Типа Среднего И Пожилого Возраста. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 4(6), 274-276.
- 27.Toxirovna, E. G. (2023). O'RTA VA KEKSA YOSHLI BEMORLARDA 2-TUR QANDLI DIABET KESHISHINING KLINIKO-MORFOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 33(1), 164-166.
- 28.Ergasheva, G. T. (2022). QANDLI DIABET BILAN KASALLANGANLARDA REABILITATSIYA MEZONLARINI TAKOMILASHTIRISH. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(12), 335-337.
- 29.Ergasheva, G. (2024). METHODS TO PREVENT SIDE EFFECTS OF DIABETES MELLITUS IN SICK PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES. Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана, 1(2), 12-16.

30. ГТ, Э., & Саидова, Л. Б. (2022). СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИОННО-ВОССТАНОВИТЕЛЬНЫХ КРИТЕРИЕВ БОЛЬНЫХ С СД-2 ТИПА. ТА'ЛИМ VA RIVOJLANISH TANLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(12), 206-209.
31. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). MUSHAKLAR TO'GRISIDA MA'LUMOT. MUSHAKLARNING TARAQQIYOTI. MUSHAKLARNING YORDAMCHI APPARATI. TADQIQOTLAR. UZ, 40(3), 94-100.
32. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). APPLICATION OF MYOCARDIAL CYTOPROTECTORS IN ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASES. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 39(5), 152-159.
33. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). SIGNIFICANCE OF BIOMARKERS IN METABOLIC SYNDROME. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 4(9), 409-413.
34. Zikrillaev, F. A. (2024). Cardiorehabilitations from Physiotherapeutic Treatments in Cardiovascular Diseases. American Journal of Bioscience and Clinical Integrity, 1(10), 96-102.
35. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). Cardiovascular System. Heart. Aorta. Carotid Artery.
36. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). MORPHO-FUNCTIONAL ASPECTS OF THE DEEP VEINS OF THE HUMAN BRAIN. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 36(6), 203-206.
37. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). ASTRAGAL O'SIMLIGINING TIBBIYOTDAGI MUHIM ANAMIYATLARI VA SOG'LOM TURMUSH TARZIGA TA'SIRI. Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования, 14(4), 111-119.
38. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). O DAM ANATOMIYASI FANIDAN SINDESMOLOGIYA BO'LIMI HAQIDA UMUMIY MALUMOTLAR. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 41(4), 37-45.
39. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ASTRAGAL PLANT IN MEDICINE AND ITS EFFECT ON A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 41(4), 88-95.
40. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). Department of Syndesmology from the Science of Human Anatomy General Information About. Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies, 3(3), 158-165.
41. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). THE COMPLEXITY OF THE FUSION OF THE BONES OF THE FOOT. JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH, 3(5), 223-230.
42. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). ANATOMICAL COMPLEXITIES OF JOINT BONES OF THE HAND. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 4(4), 198-206.
43. Зикриллаев, Ф. А. (2024). АНАТОМИЧЕСКОЕ СТРОЕНИЕ ОРГАНОВ ДЫХАНИЯ И ЕГО ЛИЧНЫЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ. TADQIQOTLAR. UZ, 40(3), 86-93.
44. Abdurashitovich, Z. F., & Komoliddinovich, S. J. (2024). DIGESTIVE SYSTEM. ANATOMY OF THE STOMACH. TADQIQOTLAR. UZ, 40(3), 78-85.
45. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). UMURTQA POG'ONASI BIRLASHUVLARI. TADQIQOTLAR. UZ, 40(3), 40-47.
46. Rakhmatova, D. B., & Zikrillaev, F. A. (2022). DETERMINE THE VALUE OF RISK FACTORS FOR MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION. FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA JURNALI | JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION, CULTURE AND INNOVATION, 1(4), 23-28.
47. Saloxiddinova, X. Y., & Ne'matillaeva, X. M. (2024). FEATURES OF THE STRUCTURE OF THE REPRODUCTIVE ORGANS OF THE FEMALE BODY. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 179-183.

- 48.Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЛИЦ ЗЛОУПОТРЕБЛЯЮЩЕЕСЯ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИМИ НАПИТКАМИ. TADQIQOTLAR. UZ, 40(5), 199-207.
- 49.Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ВНУТРЕННИХ ОРГАНОВ У ЛИЦ, СТРАДАЮЩИХ АЛКОГОЛЬНОЙ ЗАВИСИМОСТЬЮ. TADQIQOTLAR. UZ, 40(5), 240-250.
- 50.Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). кафедра Клинических наук Азиатский международный университет Бухара, Узбекистан. Modern education and development, 10(1), 60-75.
- 51.Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). МОРФО-ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ И КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КОЖНЫХ ПОКРОВОВ. Modern education and development, 10(1), 76-90.
- 52.Nematilloevna, K. M., & Salokhiddinovna, K. Y. (2024). IMPORTANT FEATURES IN THE FORMATION OF DEGREE OF COMPARISON OF ADJECTIVES IN LATIN. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 150-157.
- 53.KHALIMOVA, Y. S. (2024). MORPHOFUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TESTICULAR AND OVARIAN TISSUES OF ANIMALS IN THE AGE ASPECT. Valeology: International Journal of Medical Anthropology and Bioethics, 2(9), 100-105.
- 54.Salokhiddinovna, K. Y., Saifiloevich, S. B., Barnoevich, K. I., & Hikmatov, A. S. (2024). THE INCIDENCE OF AIDS, THE DEFINITION AND CAUSES OF THE DISEASE. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 195-205.
- 55.Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). ОСОБЕННОСТИ СОЗРЕВАНИЕ И ФУНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЕ ЯИЧНИКОВ. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 188-194.
- 56.Хафизова, М. Н., & Халимова, Ю. С. (2024). МОТИВАЦИОННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ЛАТЫНИ И МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 165-171.
- 57.Хафизова, М. Н., & Халимова, Ю. С. (2024). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЧАСТОТНЫХ ОТРЕЗКОВ В НАИМЕНОВАНИЯХ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ В ФАРМАЦЕВТИКЕ. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 172-178.

